

Disabilities and Care Needs among Older People: Evidence from Vietnam

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Abstract

The article¹ presents the results of a scientific study on disability among elderly people (aged 60 and older) based on data from “The Vietnam National Disability Survey 2016 (VNDS 2016)”, which was the most recent publicly available data at the time of our analysis. The aim of the study was to analyze the need for care among elderly individuals with disabilities². The findings indicate that approximately 10% of elderly people in Vietnam require care, which is equivalent to about 1.2 million individuals. The proportion of those in need of care is 29% among elderly people with disabilities and 53.8% among those with severe disabilities. Additionally, we found that 31% and 12% of elderly individuals live with moderate and severe disabilities, respectively. These figures are significantly higher than the disability rates officially recognized by local authorities.

The results of probit and logit regressions show that disability is more prevalent among elderly individuals and women. There is a strong negative correlation between education and disability, as well as between socioeconomic status and disability. This study provides several policy recommendations for modifying Vietnam’s existing social protection system.

Keywords

disability, older people, care need, inequality, health care, Vietnam

JEL codes: J14; I18; J18

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2 The views and analysis presented in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of their affiliations

Introduction

With economic development and advancements in medicine, human health and longevity have greatly improved. Concurrently, fertility rates have declined. Over the last 50 years, the total fertility rate (births per woman) worldwide has halved, dropping to 2.4 in 2017 (World Bank 2018). Increased life expectancy and declining birth rates have contributed to the global trend of population aging. According to forecasts from the United Nations (2019), the proportion of people aged 65 and over is projected to increase from 9% in 2019 to 16% in 2050. In 2018, for the first time in history, the number of people aged 65 and over exceeded the number of children under 5. Numerous studies discuss the socio-economic consequences of population aging (e.g., Lee 2014; Otsu and Shibayama 2016; Maestas et al. 2023). One of the main challenges of population aging is how to provide healthcare for the elderly (Reynolds et al. 2022; Xie et al. 2023; Dent et al. 2023). The number of older people needing care and those with unmet needs is projected to increase in the future (Kalánková et al. 2021; Gong et al. 2022; Rahman et al. 2022). Understanding the care needs of elderly individuals, especially those with disabilities, is crucial not only for researchers but also for policymakers responsible for social issues.

Viet Nam is among the most rapidly aging countries in the world. According to the General Statistics Office (GSO 2019), the aging index, which is the ratio of the number of people aged 60 and above to the number of children below 15 (measured as a percentage), has increased over time. The aging index rose by 13.3 percentage points from 35.5% in 2009 to 48.8% in 2019. Estimates from the 2019 Vietnam Population and Housing Census indicate that there are nearly 12 million people aged 60 and over in Vietnam, accounting for 12.2% of the total population. It is predicted that by 2035, Viet Nam will have an aged population with 20% of the total population being people aged 60 and above (World Bank 2018). Additionally, around 9% of adults (aged 15 and above) in Vietnam have disabilities (GSO 2018). Results from the 2016 Vietnam National Disability Survey show that almost 80% of people living with disabilities (PLWD) in Viet Nam are older people aged 60 and above. The high disability rate among older persons necessitates special attention to care.

In this study, we examine the prevalence of disability and care needs among older people, particularly those with disabilities, using the 2016 Vietnam National Disability Survey (VNDS 2016). Our study has two main objectives. Firstly, it provides evidence on disabilities among older persons, including the prevalence, trends, and situation of older persons living with disabilities (henceforth referred to as OPLWD). Secondly, it examines the care needs and access to healthcare and social protection for older people and OPLWD in Vietnam. The analysis is disaggregated by sex, age, rural-urban residence, region, employment status, marital status, education, ethnicity, and welfare level (wealth index). This study is expected to provide useful information for the government to take immediate actions to ensure better support and access to social protection measures for older people in Viet Nam, promoting healthy, active, and fulfilling lives.

Several studies have examined disability using household surveys in Vietnam. Using the 2006 Vietnam Household Living Standard Survey, Mont and Nguyen (2011) show a strong association between disability and poverty, with this disability-poverty link being associated with lower educational attainment. Using the same dataset, Mont and Nguyen (2013) find a negative effect of parental disability on the education of their children. Minh et al. (2015) conducted a survey in eight provinces in 2011 and estimated the extra cost of living with a disability in Vietnam. The cost is estimated at around 8.8-9.5% of annual household income, equivalent to US\$200-218. The General Statistics Office (GSO 2018) used the 2016 Vietnam National Disability Survey to estimate the prevalence of disability in Vietnam and the characteristics of households with

members living with disabilities. More recently, Le et al. (2020) examined the gender gap in disability among older people in Vietnam using the 2011 Vietnam Aging Survey.

The care needs of older people in Vietnam have also been studied extensively. For instance, Bang et al. (2017) examine the health status and demand for healthcare among older people in a district in Hanoi. Hoi et al. (2012) assess the willingness to pay for nursing services using a sample of 2,240 households in Ha Tay province in 2007. Perhaps the most related study to the care needs of older people in Vietnam is by Hoi et al. (2011). Using the same dataset as Hoi et al. (2012), Hoi et al. (2011) investigate the requirement for assistance in activities of daily living (ADLs) among older people. The study reveals that the majority of older people do not require assistance. The proportion of older people requiring assistance is highest for advanced or intellectual ADLs (13–32%), followed by instrumental ADLs (3–13%), and basic ADLs (3–8%)³. Three-fifths of older people who require assistance receive support, primarily from their children and grandchildren, who serve as the main caregivers. This finding implies that two-fifths of older people have unmet needs. Recently, Giang et al. (2020), using the 2011 Vietnam Aging Survey, found that social support can reduce the likelihood of older people experiencing limitations in ADLs.

In this study, due to data limitations, we cannot estimate the unmet needs. Instead, we focus on the care needs among older people and those with disabilities. The main advantage of our study is the use of a current and nationally representative dataset compared to previous studies on disability in Vietnam. The 2016 Vietnam National Disability Survey offers representative data at the national level, as well as for urban/rural areas and the six geographical regions of Vietnam. Using this dataset, we can provide more updated and detailed insights into the disability and care needs of older people in Vietnam.

This article is structured into five sections. The second section presents the dataset and methodology used to measure disability and the care needs of older people. The third section provides an analysis of disability among older people in Vietnam. The fourth section examines the care needs and access to healthcare and social protection for older people and those living with disabilities (OPLWD) in Vietnam. Finally, the fifth section summarizes the main findings of this study and suggests several policy recommendations for improving social policy regarding elderly care in the country.

Measurement of disability and care needs of older people

Data set

This study relies on data from the Viet Nam National Disability Survey (VNDS), which was conducted by the General Statistics Office in late 2016 and early 2017⁴. The sample frame of the 2016 VNDS is based on the Intercensal Population and Housing Survey 2014. The

3 According to Malazonia et al. (2021), the functional status of individuals can be assessed at three levels: Basic activities of daily living (BADLs), instrumental or intermediate activities of daily living (IADLs), and advanced activities of daily living (AADLs). Basic ADLs refer to self-care activities such as bathing, dressing, toileting, feeding, while instrumental ADLs refer to the activities to maintain an independent household such as shopping, cooking, doing housework, financing households. Advanced ADLs encompass the activities to meet societal, community, and familial obligations such as in recreational or occupational activities.

4 The 2016 VNDS is the first Viet Nam National Disability Survey. The second National Disability Survey was conducted in 2023. At the time of conducting this study, we did not have access to this survey. Therefore, for this study, we utilize data from the 2016 VNDS.

2016 VNDS follows a two-step stratified sampling method. First, 1,074 enumeration areas were sampled from 126 strata (urban/rural and provinces). Then, 33 households were randomly selected from each enumeration area (more details on the sampling method can be found in GSO (2018)). This survey covers 35,442 households from 1,074 enumeration areas in 1,074 communes and wards across 658 districts throughout the country⁵. The response rate is 98.8%. Thus, the final sample of households for analysis is 35,029. This sample is representative at the national level, for urban and rural areas, and for the six geographic regions (Red River Delta, North Midland and Mountain, North Central and Central Coast, Central Highlands, South East, and Mekong River Delta).

In this study, we focus on individuals aged 60 and older, who are defined as older people according to the 2009 Vietnam Law on the Elderly. In the 2016 VNDS, there are 11,072 households that have at least one older member. The sample size of individuals aged 60 and older is 15,372. We primarily use this sample for our analysis.

The 2016 VNDS contains both household-level and individual-level data. Household-level data include information on housing conditions and durable goods ownership, but there are no data on income or consumption. The individual-level data are more detailed and include information on demographics, education, healthcare, labor, and social inclusion. Notably, there are comprehensive data on disability and functional limitations of individuals.

Since the 2016 VNDS lacks data on income or consumption, we utilize the principal components approach developed by Filmer and Pritchett (2001) to measure the welfare level of households. We construct a wealth index for households using this method. An aggregate asset index is formed as the first principal component of a vector of household assets, which includes durable goods, housing characteristics, and access to utilities⁶. Using the estimated wealth index, we classify households into wealth quintiles.

Measurement of disability

Disability is a multifaceted phenomenon and can be measured in various ways. Recently, disability has been assessed based on the level of difficulty individuals experience in performing various activities (Mont 2007a, 2007b; Mont and Nguyen 2011). The Washington Group on Disability Statistics (WGDS) recommends using the presence of difficulties in a core set of basic activities, including sight, hearing, walking, cognition, communication, and

5 There are 63 provinces and provincial-level cities in Vietnam. Each province is split into districts, and each district is split further into communes and wards. In 2016, there were 713 districts and 11,162 communes and wards.

6 The principal component approach defines a wealth index in terms of the first principal component of the variables used (Filmer and Pritchett 2001; Kolenikov and Angeles 2009). The wealth index, denoted by A_j , for

household j is computed as follows: $A_j = \sum_p a_p \left(\frac{x_{pj} - \bar{x}_p}{s_p} \right)$, where x_p denotes the asset p , and \bar{x} denote

a mean of households in the sample. S_p is a standard deviation of asset x_p , and the weight a_p is chosen to maximize

the sample variance of A , subject to $\sum_p a_p^2 = 1$. The weight a is also called the vector of scores of asset variables,

which can be estimated using principal component analysis. The asset index is standardized to have zero mean and standard deviation of one. Using this asset index, we classify households by quintile from the group with the lowest asset index to the group with the highest asset index. Based on the data availability, assets, which are used to construct the wealth index, include solid pillar, solid floor, solid roof, solid wall, piped water, improved latrine, access to grid electricity, radio, television, telephone, fridge, computer, internet connection, air conditioner, washing machine, motorbike, car, and boat.

self-care, as an operational proxy for identifying individuals at risk of disability (Washington Group on Disability Statistics 2010)⁷. In the case of Vietnam, several household surveys, including the 2006 Vietnam Household Living Standard Survey, the 2009 Population and Housing Census, and the 2016 VNDS, have utilized this approach to collect data and measure disabilities. Recently, the General Statistics Office (GSO 2018) also employed this approach in conjunction with the 2016 VNDS to analyze disability in Vietnam.

In this study, we also adopt the approach recommended by the Washington Group on Disability Statistics (WGDS) to measure disability among older people in Vietnam. We begin by defining disability based on six primary functional domains: seeing, hearing, walking, cognition, communication, and self-care. Data are collected using the Washington Group Short Set questions, where respondents are asked about the level of difficulty they may encounter when performing certain activities related to these six domains. For example, they may be asked, “Do you have difficulty seeing even if wearing glasses?” Interviewees can select one of four response options: a. No difficulty; b. Some difficulty; c. A lot of difficulty; and d. Cannot do at all. A person is classified as having a disability if they report “a lot of difficulty” or “cannot do at all” in at least one functional domain. Table A1 in the Appendix presents the primary questions used to identify difficulty in the six domains.

A limitation of the WGSS is that it does not consider psychological issues and upper body mobility. To address this, the Washington Group on Disability Statistics (WGDS) extends the short set to include these additional domains. The extended set questions of the WGDS encompass the same six domains as the WGSS short set, along with new questions on psychological issues and upper body mobility. Therefore, the WGDS extended set consists of eight functional domains. A person is considered to have a disability if they report “a lot of difficulty” or “cannot do at all” in at least one functional domain. For psychological issues, a person is considered to have a disability if they experience problems with both high frequency and intensity (a lot of difficulty on a daily basis).

In this study, we measure disability among older people using both the short and extended set definitions recommended by the WGDS. This approach is also used by the General Statistics Office (GSO 2018). Additionally, we measure a high level of disability using the WGDS extended set definition.

Care needs among older people

Older people have more frequent and complex care needs than younger individuals due to disability and other health problems (Herr et al. 2013). The concept of need is crucial for understanding how social policies and programs are designed and provided for older people, especially those with disabilities (Vlachantoni 2019). The effectiveness of public services is assessed by the extent to which the care needs of older people are met. Defining and measuring care needs is also useful for determining eligibility criteria for older people to receive public services and assistance (Vlachantoni et al. 2011).

Several studies distinguish between more objective needs, such as normative and clinical needs identified by experts, and subjective needs expressed and assessed by individuals themselves (Bradshaw 1972; Allin et al. 2010). Care needs can also be assessed from

7 The approach is similar to the model that underlies the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health, which focuses on people’s ability to take certain activities in their current environment (WHO 2011; Altman 2001).

the perspective of caregivers (Miranda-Castillo et al. 2013). Recent studies have discussed care needs in relation to individuals' difficulties in functional domains or performing daily activities (e.g., Vlachantoni et al. 2011; Allen et al. 2014; Kingston et al. 2018). The care needs of older people arise when they face difficulties in daily activities and cannot live independently.

A common framework for measuring care needs among older people includes activities of daily living (ADLs) and instrumental activities of daily living (IADLs) (Spector et al. 1987; Williams et al. 1997). Katz and Akpom (1976) developed a set of measures for limitations in basic daily activities such as bathing, dressing, toileting, moving from bed, eating, and continence. Long-term care needs might be estimated for people who experience a number of ADL limitations (Williams et al. 1997). IADLs measure the ability to perform periodic activities such as transportation, shopping, meal preparation, and household chores (Williams et al. 1997).

ADLs are necessary for individuals' self-care in everyday life, while IADLs are important for functioning in their households and communities (Gill et al. 2004). Individuals with difficulty in ADLs require care and assistance from others, either from formal or informal providers. People will report 'unmet needs' when help and assistance are unavailable or insufficient for these activities (Williams et al. 1997). Long-term unmet needs can have serious consequences for older people, such as hospitalizations, psychological distress, more severe health problems, and mortality (e.g., see Allen and Mor 1997; LaPlante et al. 2004; Gureje et al. 2006; Quail et al. 2011; Momtaz et al. 2012).

The 2016 VNDS is designed to measure disability rather than ADLs or IADLs. Among the functional domains used to measure disability according to the Washington Group on Disability Statistics, there is a self-care domain that asks respondents whether they have difficulty with self-care tasks such as washing all over or dressing. While the self-care domain is related to ADLs, the information from the 2016 VNDS cannot fully capture the comprehensive measurement of ADLs or IADLs. Therefore, in this study, we focus on the care needs among older people with disabilities instead of those with difficulties in ADLs or IADLs.

The 2016 VNDS does not provide sufficient information to measure unmet needs of older people. In this study, we are only able to measure the care needs of older people with disabilities. There is a question in the 2016 VNDS that asks respondents whether they need someone to provide care and assistance for their daily activities, such as eating, bathing, toileting, and mobility. Respondents who answer 'Yes' are defined as those who need care help.

Disability among older people

Prevalence of disability in Vietnam

Healthcare and support for the elderly and people with disabilities have garnered significant attention from policymakers in Vietnam. The Vietnam Law on the Elderly, promulgated by the National Assembly in 2009, defines the rights and obligations of the elderly as well as the responsibilities of the State and social agencies for their care. To improve access to healthcare for older people, the government has implemented the National Program of Action on the elderly population of Vietnam for the period 2012-2020 (Decision No.1781/QD-TTg on 11/22/2012).

Regarding disability, Vietnam passed the Law on People with Disabilities in 2010 and has issued related decisions to implement this law. People with disabilities and older people are entitled to reductions in fees for several public services, such as transportation and health-care (Government of Vietnam 2012). The most significant supports for people with high disabilities and those aged 80 and older include free health insurance and monthly social allowances.

According to the Law on the Elderly, older people are defined as those aged 60 years and above. In this study, we use this definition to identify older people in the dataset. In the 2016 VNDS, 12.9% of individuals are aged 60 and over. Individuals below 60 are excluded from the analysis.

As mentioned in section 2.2, we measure disability among older people using both the WGDS short and extended sets of functional domains. Additionally, we define high disability using the WGDS extended set.

We begin with a descriptive analysis of the proportion of older people with difficulty in different domains (Table 1). 6.8% and 5.4% of older people have difficulty in seeing and hearing, respectively. The proportion of older people who reported “cannot do at all” in seeing and hearing is 0.7% and 0.5%, respectively.

There are more older people with difficulty in low mobility (walking), at 14.6%. In the WGDS extended set, there are more sub-questions on low mobility, and a person is defined as having a disability if they have difficulty in each sub-domain of the low mobility domain (see Table A1 in Appendix). As a result, the prevalence of older people with difficulty in low mobility using the WGDS extended set is higher than when using the WGDS short set, at 25.7%. The share of older people with high difficulty in low mobility is 6.6%. There is a significantly lower proportion of older people with difficulty in high mobility. 12.4% of older people have difficulty, and 5.8% of older people have high difficulty, in high mobility.

Table 1. Proportion and number of older people with difficulty in functional domains

Functional domains	Disability using short set of WGDS		Disability using extended set of WGDS		Disability using extended set of WGDS (High threshold)	
	% people with difficulty	Number of people (thousand)	% people with difficulty	Number of people (thousand)	% people with difficulty	Number of people (thousand)
Vision	6.8	807.3	6.8	807.3	0.7	83.1
Hearing	5.4	641.1	5.4	641.1	0.5	59.4
Low mobility	14.6	1733.3	25.7	3051.1	6.6	783.6
High mobility	n.a.	n.a.	12.4	1472.1	5.8	688.6
Cognitive	8.2	973.5	9.6	1139.7	5.6	664.8
Communication	2.8	332.4	2.8	332.4	0.6	71.2
Self-care	6.9	819.2	6.9	819.2	3.9	463.0
Psycho-social	n.a.	n.a.	1.5	178.1	1.5	178.1

Source: Estimation from the 2016 VNDS.

The proportion of older people with cognitive disabilities using the short set definition is 8.2%. When the extended set is used, this rate is slightly higher, at 9.6%. There are 2.8% of older people who have difficulty in communication. There is also a small proportion of older people with psycho-social disabilities, at 1.5%.

As mentioned, self-care is more related to ADLs than other functional domains. There are 6.9% of older people who have difficulty in self-care (around 820 thousand people). The proportion of older people with high difficulty in self-care is 3.9% (around 460 thousand people).

A person is defined as living with disabilities if they have difficulty in at least one functional domain. According to GSO (2018), which also uses the same dataset as this study, the national rate of disability is estimated at 5.72% using the WGDS short set and 8.64% using the WGDS extended set. Figure 1 shows the proportion of older people with disabilities: 21.1% using the WGDS short set and 30.7% using the WGDS extended set. The number of older people with disabilities using these two definitions is estimated at 2.51 million and 3.65 million, respectively. When the high threshold of difficulty is used, 11.9% of older people are found to have high difficulty in at least one functional domain (around 1.4 million people).

Figure 1. The percentage and the number of older people with disabilities. *Source:* Estimation from the 2016 VNDS.

The severity of disability can be examined through the number of functional limitations older people with disabilities experience. For those defined by the WGDS extended set, the average number of functional limitations is 2.31. For people with high disability, this number is 2.1. Figure 2 shows the distribution of older people with disabilities by the number of domains in which they have difficulty. It reveals that 45.9% of older individuals with disabilities have difficulties in one domain, 20.4% encounter challenges in two domains,

and 13.4% face difficulties in three domains. The proportion of older people with disabilities experiencing difficulty in six or more domains is 7.3%. Among older people with a high level of disability, 2.4% encounter difficulties in six or more domains.

Figure 2. The percentage and the number of older people with disabilities. *Source:* Estimation from the 2016 VNDS.

To receive support, individuals must be identified as disabled by local authorities. The government has provided regulations on determining disability levels through a local council. The 2016 VNDS contains information on disabilities classified by local authorities. Approximately 3% of older people are identified as disabled by local authorities⁸. These individuals possess disability certificates provided by local authorities, certifying the type and extent of their disability. It’s important to note that this group does not include people with disabilities caused by wars.

There are two additional groups of older people with disabilities, including war invalids (accounting for 3.8% of older people) and victims of “Agent Orange” (1.2%). There is very little overlap between these three groups. The proportion of older people who are war invalids, victims of “Agent Orange”, or disabled according to local authorities is 6.8%. This rate is remarkably lower than the rate of disability measured by the WGDS approach.

Figure 3 illustrates the overlap between disability defined by the WGDS extended set and disability identified by local authorities, war invalids, and “Agent Orange” victims. For simplicity, we combine the war invalids and “Agent Orange” victims into one group.

There is a relatively large overlap between disability defined by the WGDS extended set and disability identified by local authorities. However, there is a significant proportion

⁸ According to MOLISA (2019), when there is a need to determine the level of disability, the individual with a disability submits an application to the People’s Committee of the commune where they reside. The People’s Committee will establish a council with medical and disability expertise to assess the level of disability. The Council directly observes individuals with disabilities, implementing simple activities to address personal daily living needs. They employ a set of questions based on medical and social criteria, as well as other simple methods, to determine the type and level of disability for each person with a disability.

of older people with disabilities (identified by the WGDS extended set) who are not classified as disabled or as war invalids or “Agent Orange” victims by local authorities.

Figure 3. Overlap between WGDS disability and disability identified by local authorities. *Source:* Estimation from the 2016 VNDS.

Conversely, there is a proportion of older people who are identified as disabled or as war invalids or “Agent Orange” victims by local authorities but are not found to be disabled by the WGDS approach. This raises concerns about the coverage and leakage of the identification of disability by local authorities in Vietnam.

Disability prevalence by different groups

In this section, the analysis of disability prevalence is disaggregated by demographic and socio-economic characteristics of older people. Disability is measured using both the WGDS short and extended sets, with people defined as disabled if they have difficulty in at least one functional domain. Additionally, we examine people who face difficulty in at least two functional domains.

Across all disability measures, age is strongly correlated with the disability rate. Women exhibit higher rates of disability than men. Given the relatively large gap in life expectancy between men and women in Vietnam, women tend to have a higher average age, leading to a higher likelihood of disability. While ethnic minorities display a higher rate of disability than the Kinh majority, this gap is small and not statistically significant at the 5% level. Rural older people exhibit a higher rate of disability than urban counterparts.

Older people are disaggregated by their current marital status. Widowed individuals exhibit the highest rate of disability, largely because this group tends to be older than the others. Unmarried individuals display a higher rate of disability compared to married and divorced individuals. This could potentially stem from inverse causality: individuals with disabilities may encounter greater difficulty in finding a spouse.

Moreover, people living alone demonstrate a higher rate of disability than those living with others. For instance, 44.9% of individuals living alone experience difficulty in at least one domain of the WGDS extended set, whereas this rate is 30.8% for those not living alone. The primary reason for this discrepancy is that individuals living alone tend to be older and more likely to be widowed. This observation aligns with existing research indicating that single individuals have a higher rate of disability than married individuals.

Table 2. Proportion of older people with disabilities by demographic characteristics

Population groups	Disability definition using WGDS short set		Disability definition using WGDS extended set		Disability definition using WGDS extended set and high threshold	
	Difficulty in at least one domain	Difficulty in at least two domains	Difficulty in at least one domain	Difficulty in at least two domains	Difficulty in at least one domain	Difficulty in at least two domains
<i>All older people</i>	21.1	11.0	30.7	16.6	11.9	6.1
<i>Age groups</i>						
60-64	7.0	2.4	12.1	4.0	3.9	1.2
65-69	12.9	5.3	21.8	8.5	7.3	2.9
70-74	19.2	9.0	29.9	13.7	9.1	4.4
75-79	29.1	13.5	42.6	21.5	13.9	6.0
80+	53.3	33.9	69.1	48.7	33.2	20.2
<i>Gender</i>						
Female	23.1	12.3	34.2	18.7	13.5	7.0
Male	18.2	9.3	25.9	13.7	9.9	4.8
<i>Urban/rural</i>						
Rural	23.8	12.5	34.6	18.9	13.1	6.5
Urban	15.7	8.3	23.1	12.1	9.7	5.2
<i>Ethnicity</i>						
Ethnic minorities	22.6	12.5	30.7	18.4	13.8	5.5
Kinh	20.9	10.9	30.7	16.4	11.7	6.1
<i>Marital status</i>						
Single	25.2	16.3	32.6	19.9	16.8	9.6
Married	15.3	6.9	23.4	10.8	8.0	3.6
Widowed	32.5	19.0	45.5	28.1	19.4	10.7
Divorced or separate	15.7	8.5	23.1	11.9	9.1	5.8
<i>Living</i>						
Living alone	30.9	16.2	44.9	25.3	16.3	7.1
Living with dependants (child or older)	20.9	9.8	30.8	15.6	11.5	5.3

Population groups	Disability definition using WGDS short set		Disability definition using WGDS extended set		Disability definition using WGDS extended set and high threshold	
	Difficulty in at least one domain	Difficulty in at least two domains	Difficulty in at least one domain	Difficulty in at least two domains	Difficulty in at least one domain	Difficulty in at least two domains
Living with at least a member 15-59	19.8	10.8	28.7	15.8	11.5	6.2
<i>Wealth index quintile</i>						
Poorest	33.3	18.0	46.5	26.9	18.2	9.2
Near poorest	21.2	10.6	31.9	16.1	12.0	5.8
Middle	18.3	9.5	27.6	14.1	10.2	5.2
Near richest	15.2	7.5	22.7	12.1	8.6	4.8
Richest	11.0	6.2	16.4	8.8	7.5	3.9

Source: Estimation from the 2016 VNDS.

Consistent with previous studies on disabilities in Vietnam, such as Mont and Nguyen (2011) and GSO (2018), we observe that individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, including those classified as poor and those in low expenditure quintiles, have higher rates of disability compared to their wealthier counterparts. For instance, the disability rate, based on one domain of difficulty and the WGDS extended set, is 50.4% for poor individuals and 28.5% for non-poor individuals. Older people in the lowest wealth quintile exhibit a disability rate of 46.5%, whereas those in the highest wealth quintile have a disability rate of 16.4%.

It's evident that older individuals who are both impoverished and disabled are particularly vulnerable and should receive support from the government.

Regression analysis

In this section, we employ regression analysis to gain deeper insights into the association between socio-economic characteristics and disability among older people. Age, being a key determinant of disability, is often correlated with many socio-economic factors among older individuals. Therefore, the observed association between disability and socio-economic characteristics may be influenced by age.

We regress the binary variable indicating disability status of older people on a set of explanatory variables. For simplicity, we utilize the WGDS extended set to define an older person as living with a disability if they experience difficulty in at least one domain. Additionally, an older person is classified as having high disability if they report the highest level of difficulty (cannot do at all) in at least one domain.

The explanatory variables include demographic and socio-economic characteristics of older people, as well as urban and regional dummies. Table A2 in the Appendix provides a summary of the basic statistics of both the dependent and explanatory variables.

Since the dependent variables are binary, we employ both probit and logit models for our analysis. We present results from both models. To aid interpretation, we compute the marginal effect of explanatory variables in the probit model and odds ratios in the logit model⁹. In this article, we primarily utilize the estimates of the marginal effect from the probit model for interpretation.

It's important to note that a positive marginal effect of an explanatory variable indicates a positive association between this variable and the probability of having a disability. In such cases, the odds ratio derived from the logit model will be larger than 1. Conversely, negative marginal effects in the probit model imply odds ratios below 1.

It's essential to acknowledge that the regression analysis conducted in this study serves to unveil the association between disability and socio-economic characteristics among older people. However, it's crucial to recognize that estimating the causal effect of socio-economic characteristics on disability is inherently challenging due to potential issues such as reverse causality and omitted variable bias.

Disability itself can influence the socio-economic outcomes of individuals, leading to a bi-directional relationship between disability and socio-economic factors. Moreover, there may exist unobserved variables that are correlated with both disability and the explanatory variables included in the regression model. These unobserved factors can confound the estimated effects of socio-economic characteristics on the probability of disability among older people.

Given these complexities, it becomes difficult to disentangle the causal effects of socio-economic variables on disability with certainty, especially in observational studies. Therefore, while regression analysis provides valuable insights into the association between disability and socio-economic factors, caution must be exercised in interpreting these results as causal relationships.

There is a U-shaped relationship between disability and age. As age increases, the probability of disability rises with an increasing rate. This aligns with the descriptive analysis indicating a substantial increase in the disability rate among individuals aged 80 and above.

The variable 'male' is negative and significant in the regression of disability (column 1 in Table 3). The probability of disability is 0.0237 lower for men than for women. Utilizing the logit result (column 3), we interpret that the odds of disability for men are 0.89 times that for women. Disability is more prevalent among women than men, even when controlling for age and other observed variables. This finding is consistent with previous studies conducted in both low – and high-income countries (see review by Leveille et al. 2000). Possible reasons include a higher prevalence of non-fatal chronic conditions and constitutional factors such as lower muscle strength and bone density among women (Leveille et al. 2000). In the context of Vietnam, Mont and Nguyen (2011), GSO (2018), Le et al. (2020), and Van Tran et al. (2022) have also documented a higher rate of disability among women compared to men.

There are no significant differences in the probability of disability between the Kinh majority and ethnic minorities. Although the descriptive analysis indicates a higher rate of disability among ethnic minorities, this discrepancy disappears once the observed characteristics of older people are taken into account. This suggests that the disparity in disability between the Kinh majority and ethnic minorities can be attributed to differences in the explanatory variables used in the regressions.

9 Overall, both logit and probit models produce very similar results. Researchers from different fields might be more familiar with one of the two models. For example, economists are more familiar with the interpretation from the probit model, while medical researchers are more familiar with the interpretation from the logit model.

Married individuals are less likely to have a disability compared to other groups. The widowed, divorced, and separated individuals have a lower probability of disability than the single group (the reference group). This could be a result of reverse causality, as individuals with disabilities might find it more challenging to get married. Consequently, the rate of disability among this group is higher than among other groups.

There is a strong and negative association between education and disability, indicative of a two-way relationship. Lower levels of education may lead to decreased income and heightened risk of illness and disability. Conversely, individuals with disabilities may encounter difficulties in attending school and acquiring education, thus reducing their likelihood of attaining higher levels of education.

There appears to be no significant association between household size and disability. However, older individuals who live alone exhibit a lower probability of disability compared to others. This is likely because people with disabilities often require care and are more likely to reside with caregivers, such as children and grandchildren.

Previous studies such as Kashcheeva (2019), Fokina et al. (2020), Silver and Zhang (2022), and Pu and Syu (2023) have demonstrated a negative association between disability and wealth. Consistent with these findings, our study also reveals that older individuals in higher wealth quintiles exhibit a lower probability of disability as well as high disability compared to those in lower quintiles. Wealthier individuals tend to have better access to nutrition and healthcare, which may contribute to lower rates of disability. Conversely, individuals with disabilities often face reduced labour productivity, employment opportunities, and income compared to others.

Moreover, older individuals residing in urban areas are less likely to have a disability than those in rural areas. However, the probability of high disability does not significantly differ between urban and rural areas. Additionally, disability rates vary across regions, with the Central Coast exhibiting the highest probability of disability even after controlling for socioeconomic variables. This disparity could be attributed to factors such as the region's susceptibility to natural disasters, which may impact people's health, as well as the long-term effects of wars, as demonstrated by Palmer et al. (2019), particularly in regions heavily affected by conflict like the Central Coast.

Table 3. Regression of disability

Explanatory variables	Marginal effect from Probit		Odds ratio from Logit	
	Dependent variable is disability using WGDS extended set	Dependent variable is high disability using WGDS extended set	Dependent variable is disability using WGDS extended set	Dependent variable is high disability using WGDS extended set
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Age	0.0042	-0.0105**	1.0417	0.9610
Age squared	0.0001**	0.0001***	1.0005	1.0009***
Male (male=1; female=0)	-0.0237**	-0.0014	0.8920**	0.9764
Kinh (Kinh=1, ethnic minorities=0)	0.0848***	0.0127	1.6016***	1.1689

Explanatory variables	Marginal effect from Probit		Odds ratio from Logit	
	Dependent variable is disabil- ity using WGDS ex- tended set	Dependent variable is high dis- ability using WGDS ex- tended set	Dependent variable is disabil- ity using WGDS ex- tended set	Dependent variable is high dis- ability using WGDS ex- tended set
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Single				
Married	-0.1125***	-0.0993***	0.5609***	0.3404***
Widowed	-0.1044***	-0.0527***	0.5504***	0.4337***
Divorced or separate	-0.0852***	-0.0627***	0.6303***	0.4349***
Less than primary education				
Primary education	-0.0635***	-0.0211***	0.7208***	0.7811***
Lower-secondary education	-0.0778***	-0.0260***	0.6567***	0.7226***
Upper-secondary education	-0.1030***	-0.0350***	0.5453***	0.6157**
Post secondary education	-0.1087***	-0.0276**	0.5344***	0.7101
Living with a member aged 15-59				
Living alone	-0.0660***	-0.0344***	0.6947***	0.6198***
Living with only children and/or elderly	-0.0059	0.0073	0.9776	1.0842
Household size	-0.0048	-0.0001	0.9767	0.9976
Poorest wealth quintile				
Near-poorest wealth quintile	-0.0933***	-0.0266***	0.6091***	0.7248***
Middle wealth quintile	-0.1265***	-0.0424***	0.4921***	0.5747***
Near-richest wealth quintile	-0.1499***	-0.0505***	0.4182***	0.4960***
Richest wealth quintile	-0.1893***	-0.0553***	0.3088***	0.4601***
Urban areas (urban=1, rural=0)	-0.0285*	0.0019	0.8586*	1.0099
Red River Delta				
Northern Mountain	0.0350	0.0235	1.2017	1.2776
Central Coast	0.0813***	0.0143	1.5286***	1.1881
Central Highland	0.0167	-0.0103	1.1176	0.8855
Southeast	0.0634***	0.0326**	1.3959***	1.4546***
Mekong River Delta	0.0530**	0.0046	1.3320***	1.0811
Constant			0.0049***	0.0667
Observations	15.372	15.372	15.372	15.372
Pseudo R-squared	0.215	0.162	0.215	0.162

Source: Estimation from the 2016 VNDS. Note: Robust standard errors are corrected for sampling weight and intra-cluster correlation. To avoid lengthy results, this table does not report standard errors. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

Needs for care of older people with disabilities

Needs for care

In this section, we delve into the care needs among older individuals, particularly those with disabilities. For simplicity, we rely on a single definition of disability based on the WGDS extended set, wherein an individual is considered to be living with a disability if they experience difficulty in at least one out of the eight functional domains. Additionally, we explore high disability, which is determined by the WGDS extended set using the threshold of “cannot do it at all” to define the difficulty level in each functional domain.

Figure 4. The proportion and the number of people who need care. *Source:* Estimation from the 2016 VNDS.

In the 2016 VNDS, individuals requiring daily care are identified based on the following question: “Due to health problems, do you need someone to take care or support daily activities such as eating, bathing, and walking?” According to the survey results, approximately 10.1% of older individuals need care, totaling around 1.2 million people¹⁰. The proportion of older individuals with care needs is significantly higher among those with disabilities. Figure 4 illustrates that 1.7% of older individuals without disabilities require care, whereas among those with disabilities, this figure rises to 29%. For older individuals with high disabilities, the proportion needing care jumps to 53.8%.

Figure 5 explores which functional limitations are most strongly correlated with care needs. It reveals that older individuals facing difficulties in self-care are the most likely to require daily care, with 83.5% of them in need. Conversely, older individuals experiencing low-mobility difficulties are less likely to need care, with only 32.9% of them requiring assistance.

¹⁰ In the 2016 VNDS, there is no information on older people who need care and already received it.

Figure 5. The proportion of older people with care needs by disability in functional domains. *Source:* Estimation from the 2016 VNDS.

Table 4 displays the proportion of older individuals requiring daily care based on disability status and various demographic and socio-economic characteristics. The data illustrate a notable increase in the percentage of individuals needing care with advancing age. Roughly 30% of individuals aged 80 years and above necessitate care, whereas among those aged 60-64, only 2.7% require assistance. This trend persists even among individuals with disabilities or high disability, where the proportion of those needing care escalates significantly with age¹¹.

Females tend to require more care than males, likely due to their older age and higher likelihood of having a disability. While the proportion of older individuals needing care is comparable between the Kinh majority and ethnic minorities, Kinh individuals exhibit a higher rate of care needs among those with high disability. Considering that Kinh represent 85% of the total population, the absolute number of older individuals requiring care is substantially higher for Kinh than for ethnic minorities. Widowed individuals exhibit a higher incidence of care needs, possibly attributable to their older age compared to other groups. Additionally, older individuals living with at least one adult aged 15-59 also demonstrate a heightened rate of care needs.

Older individuals in lower wealth quintiles exhibit a higher likelihood of requiring daily care compared to those in higher wealth quintiles. This discrepancy can primarily be attributed to the higher prevalence of disability among individuals in lower wealth quintiles. However, when focusing solely on older individuals with disabilities or high disability, the

¹¹ In total, around 667 thousand people aged from 80 need daily care, of them 63 thousand people have disability and 463 thousand people have high disability.

trend reverses. In this subgroup, the rate of care needs is higher among older individuals in higher wealth quintiles compared to those in lower wealth quintiles.

Table 4. The proportion of older people who need care

Groups	Without disability	With disability	With high disability	All older people
<i>Age groups</i>				
60-64	0.8	16.3	36.3	2.7
65-69	1.0	20.1	45.5	5.2
70-74	2.7	20.7	47.8	8.1
75-79	2.6	23.3	45.3	11.4
80+	5.3	41.3	63.1	30.2
<i>Gender</i>				
Female	1.7	28.5	53.0	10.8
Male	1.7	30.0	55.2	9.0
<i>Urban/rural</i>				
Rural	1.9	27.7	53.2	10.9
Urban	1.3	32.7	55.2	8.6
<i>Ethnicity</i>				
Ethnic minorities	3.3	28.6	46.2	11.1
Kinh	1.5	29.1	54.7	10.0
<i>Marital status</i>				
Single	0.8	32.9	50.4	11.3
Married	1.4	22.1	47.6	6.2
Widowed	2.5	36.0	58.9	17.7
Divorced or separate	1.4	24.4	59.8	6.7
<i>Living</i>				
Living alone	2.7	27.9	46.8	14.0
Living with only children and/or elderly	1.3	23.4	48.4	8.1
Living with at least a member 15-59	1.7	31.3	56.9	10.2
<i>Wealth index quintile</i>				
Poorest	2.3	26.2	48.0	13.4
Near poorest	1.5	28.6	53.3	10.1
Middle	1.7	31.7	62.2	10.0
Near richest	1.6	31.2	60.8	8.3
Richest	1.3	34.7	55.5	6.8

Source: Estimation from the 2016 VNDS.

Regression analysis

Running a multivariate regression analysis allows us to explore the factors associated with the care needs of older people. We employ both probit and logit models, providing insights through marginal effects and odds ratios, respectively. Beginning with a basic model featuring age, gender, and dummy variables for functional limitations, we gradually expand the model to encompass additional social-economic characteristics of older individuals. This approach facilitates a comprehensive examination of the determinants of care needs among older people.

Table 5. Regression of ‘older people with care needs’

Explanatory variables	Marginal effect from Probit		Odds ratio from Logit	
	Small model	Large model	Small model	Large model
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Age	0.0023	0.0014	1.0745	1.0477
Age squared	0.0000	0.0000	0.9999	1.0000
Male (male=1; female=0)	0.0075*	0.0156***	1.1781*	1.4317***
Having difficulty in vision	0.0157	0.0133	1.2956*	1.2656
Having difficulty in hearing	-0.0170**	-0.0151**	0.6378**	0.6660**
Having difficulty in low mobility	0.0878***	0.0835***	4.3621***	4.2707***
Having difficulty in high mobility	0.0354***	0.0363***	1.7253***	1.7962***
Having difficulty in cognitive	0.0087	0.0077	1.1653	1.1543
Having difficulty in communication	0.0652***	0.0579**	2.6089***	2.4581***
Having difficulty in self-care	0.4126***	0.4091***	17.7472***	18.2119***
Having difficulty in psycho-social domain	0.0375	0.0407*	1.7469**	1.8378**
Kinh (Kinh=1, ethnic minorities=0)		-0.0246*		0.6309**
Single				
Married		-0.0210		0.6078*
Widowed		-0.0282***		0.3845*
Divorced or separate		-0.0055		0.8813
Less than primary education				
Primary education		-0.0052		0.9301
Lower-secondary education		-0.0157***		0.6788**
Upper-secondary education		-0.0077		0.8542
Post secondary education		-0.0041		0.8522
Living with a member aged 15-59				

Explanatory variables	Marginal effect from Probit		Odds ratio from Logit	
	Small model	Large model	Small model	Large model
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Living alone		0.0205*		1.4868**
Living with only children and/ or elderly		0.0069		1.1922
Household size		0.0026*		1.0659*
Poorest wealth quintile				
Near-poorest wealth quintile		0.0076		1.2035
Middle wealth quintile		0.0122		1.3288*
Near-richest wealth quintile		0.0103		1.2779
Richest wealth quintile		0.0051		1.1572
Urban areas (urban=1, rural=0)		-0.0022		0.9932
Red River Delta				
Northern Mountain		-0.0103		0.7754
Central Coast		0.0044		1.0922
Central Highland		-0.0106		0.7421
Southeast		0.0125		1.2650
Mekong River Delta		0.0098		1.2731
Constant			0.0003***	0.0012**
Observations	15.372	15.372	15.372	15.372
Pseudo R-squared	0.464	0.471	0.462	0.469

Source: Estimation from the 2016 VNDS. Note: Robust standard errors are corrected for sampling weight and intra-cluster correlation. To avoid lengthy results, this table does not report standard errors. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

The impact of functional limitations on care needs remains consistent across both the small and large models. Notably, difficulties in self-care exhibit the strongest correlation with care needs. Specifically, facing challenges in self-care increases the likelihood of requiring daily assistance by 0.41 (as shown in columns 1 and 2 of Table 5). Moreover, older individuals experiencing self-care difficulties are approximately 18 times more likely to need daily care compared to those without such difficulties¹². Similarly, difficulties in mobility and communication are associated with an elevated probability of needing daily assistance. However, difficulties in the cognitive domain do not yield a statistically significant association with care needs. Intriguingly, older individuals experiencing difficulties in hearing are less likely to require daily care than those without

12 The variable 'Having difficulty in self-care' is strongly correlated with the dependent variable. To assess the sensitivity of the estimates of other explanatory variables, we rerun the probit and logit regressions without including this variable. The results, reported in Table A3 in the Appendix, show similar estimates of the explanatory variables as those in Table 5.

such difficulties, warranting further investigation to elucidate the underlying reasons for this finding.

The influence of socio-economic variables on care needs appears limited, as the primary determinants are already captured by disability-related factors. While variables such as education, wealth quintiles, urban residence, and regional differences exhibit small and statistically insignificant effects on care needs, age emerges as the most crucial predictor. Although age itself is strongly correlated with care needs (as demonstrated in Table 9), its significance diminishes when disability-related variables are included in the regression.

However, gender remains a significant factor, with men exhibiting a higher likelihood of requiring daily care compared to women, even after controlling for other explanatory variables. Specifically, according to the large model, the probability of care needs among men is 0.0156 higher than that among women (as shown in column 2), translating to men being approximately 1.4317 times more likely than women to require daily care (as indicated in column 4).

Interestingly, the variable ‘widowed’ yields a negative and statistically significant effect at the 1% level (as shown in column 2). When compared to single older individuals (the reference group), widowed older individuals are less likely to require daily care. Conversely, older individuals living alone demonstrate a higher probability of needing care compared to those living in larger households.

Conclusions

Although life expectancy has increased in Vietnam, a significant proportion of older individuals grapple with disabilities. This study investigates the prevalence of disability among individuals aged 60 or older, utilizing the WGDS approach and data from the 2016 VNDS. A person is considered to have a disability if they encounter difficulty in at least one of eight functional domains. The findings reveal that 30.7% of older individuals live with disabilities, amounting to approximately 3.65 million people. Moreover, when a stricter threshold of difficulty is applied, 11.9% of older individuals are identified as experiencing severe difficulty in at least one functional domain, totaling around 1.4 million people.

We employ multivariate probit and logit regression to examine factors correlated with disability. Age emerges as a significant determinant, showcasing a pronounced effect on disability. For instance, the disability rate among individuals aged 60–64 stands at 12.1%, whereas among those aged 80 and above, it substantially rises to 69.1%. Furthermore, disability is more prevalent among women than men, even after controlling for age and other observed variables. Additionally, better-off individuals exhibit a lower probability of disability compared to those less affluent. Notably, there exists a robust and negative association between education level, wealth, and disability.

We also investigate the care needs of older people, particularly those with disabilities. About 10% of older individuals require care, totaling approximately 1.2 million people. Those with disabilities are more prone to needing assistance. Employing logistic regression, we observe that the odds of older individuals with self-care difficulties requiring care are roughly 18 times higher than those of their counterparts without such difficulties. Moreover, older individuals facing challenges in mobility and communication are also more inclined to necessitate daily care. However, difficulty in the cognitive domain does not exhibit a statistically significant association with care needs.

Vietnam is experiencing rapid population aging, making it one of the world's fastest-aging countries. Consequently, the number of older people, particularly those with disabilities requiring daily care, is steadily increasing. However, Vietnam's current social protection system only covers a fraction of the elderly population. At present, individuals aged 80 or older without regular pensions or social benefits receive a monthly allowance of 360.000 VND (approximately 14.5 USD) (Government of Vietnam 2021). To broaden the coverage to more older adults lacking regular pensions, the government might consider lowering the age threshold to 70.

Currently, individuals aged 60 and over who are impoverished and living alone receive a monthly allowance of 540.000 VND. Our study underscores that older adults with lower wealth and education are more prone to disabilities. Thus, cash transfers should not only target impoverished and isolated seniors but extend to all economically disadvantaged elderly individuals.

People with disabilities in Vietnam also receive cash transfers of 540.000 VND per month. However, a concerning issue arises from the challenges in identifying people with disabilities by local authorities in Vietnam. There is a significant disparity in the disability rate between the WGDS approach and the identification made by local authorities in Vietnam. The official disability rate is notably lower than the rate of disability measured by the WGDS approach. Conversely, there is a proportion of older people who are identified as disabled by local authorities but are not found to be disabled by the WGDS approach. It is important for the government to improve the identification of people with disabilities in Vietnam.

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Appendix

Table A1. Questions to measure disability by WGDS

The next questions ask about difficulties you may have doing certain activities (each question has four response categories, which are read after each question)

1. Do you have difficulty seeing, even if wearing glasses?

- a. No, no difficulty
 - b. Yes, some difficulty
 - c. Yes, a lot of difficulty
 - d. Cannot do it at all
-

2. Do you have difficulty hearing, even if using a hearing aid?

- a. No, no difficulty
 - b. Yes, some difficulty
 - c. Yes, a lot of difficulty
 - d. Cannot do it at all
-

3. Do you have difficulty walking or climbing steps?

- a. No, no difficulty
 - b. Yes, some difficulty
 - c. Yes, a lot of difficulty
 - d. Cannot do it at all
-

4. Do you have difficulty remembering or concentrating?

- a. No, no difficulty
 - b. Yes, some difficulty
 - c. Yes, a lot of difficulty
 - d. Cannot do it at all
-

5. Do you have difficulty (with self-care) such as washing all over or dressing?

- a. No, no difficulty
 - b. Yes, some difficulty
 - c. Yes, a lot of difficulty
 - d. Cannot do it at all
-

6. Using your usual language, do you have difficulty communicating?

- a. No, no difficulty
 - b. Yes, some difficulty
 - c. Yes, a lot of difficulty
 - d. Cannot do it at all
-

Table A2. Summary statistics of variables

Variable	Type	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Dependent variables</i>					
Disability using WGDS extended set	Binary	0.307	0.461	0	1
High disability using WGDS extended set	Binary	0.119	0.324	0	1
Older people with care needs	Binary	0.101	0.301	0	1
Older people with disabilities and care needs	Binary	0.089	0.285	0	1
Older people with high disabilities and care needs	Binary	0.064	0.245	0	1
<i>Explanatory variables</i>					
Having difficulty in vision	Binary	0.068	0.252	0	1
Having difficulty in hearing	Binary	0.054	0.226	0	1
Having difficulty in low mobility	Binary	0.257	0.437	0	1
Having difficulty in high mobility	Binary	0.124	0.329	0	1
Having difficulty in cognitive	Binary	0.096	0.295	0	1
Having difficulty in communication	Binary	0.028	0.165	0	1
Having difficulty in self-care	Binary	0.069	0.253	0	1
Having difficulty in psycho-social domain	Binary	0.015	0.121	0	1
Age	Discrete	70.422	8.945	60	109
Male (male=1; female=0)	Binary	0.420	0.494	0	1
Kinh (Kinh=1, ethnic minorities=0)	Binary	0.902	0.298	0	1
Single	Binary	0.028	0.164	0	1
Married	Binary	0.636	0.481	0	1
Widowed	Binary	0.320	0.467	0	1
Divorced or separate	Binary	0.016	0.125	0	1
Less than primary education	Binary	0.388	0.487	0	1
Primary education	Binary	0.252	0.434	0	1
Lower-secondary education	Binary	0.208	0.406	0	1
Upper-secondary education	Binary	0.099	0.299	0	1
Post secondary education	Binary	0.052	0.222	0	1
Living alone	Binary	0.093	0.290	0	1
Living with only children and/or elderly	Binary	0.231	0.421	0	1
Household size	Discrete	3.725	1.949	1	17
Poorest wealth quintile	Binary	0.255	0.436	0	1
Near-poorest wealth quintile	Binary	0.230	0.421	0	1
Middle wealth quintile	Binary	0.183	0.387	0	1
Near-richest wealth quintile	Binary	0.166	0.372	0	1
Richest wealth quintile	Binary	0.166	0.372	0	1
Urban areas (urban=1, rural=0)	Binary	0.340	0.474	0	1

Variable	Type	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Red River Delta	Binary	0.271	0.445	0	1
Northern Mountain	Binary	0.107	0.309	0	1
Central Coast	Binary	0.247	0.431	0	1
Central Highland	Binary	0.040	0.196	0	1
Southeast	Binary	0.140	0.347	0	1
Mekong River Delta	Binary	0.195	0.396	0	1
Observations		15.372			

Source: Estimation from the 2016 VNDS.

Table A3. Regression of ‘older people with care needs’ without controlling for ‘Having difficulty in self-care’

Explanatory variables	Marginal effect from Probit		Odds ratio from Logit	
	Small model	Large model	Small model	Large model
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Age	-0.0002	-0.0006	1.0199	1.0104
Age squared	0.0000	0.0000	1.0002	1.0002
Male (male=1; female=0)	0.0112***	0.0189***	1.2696***	1.5180***
Having difficulty in vision	0.0270***	0.0260***	1.4772***	1.4807***
Having difficulty in hearing	-0.0138**	-0.0119**	0.7347**	0.7601*
Having difficulty in low mobility	0.1118***	0.1090***	5.6975***	5.7077***
Having difficulty in high mobility	0.1308***	0.1306***	4.2744***	4.3926***
Having difficulty in cognitive	0.0276***	0.0273***	1.4944***	1.5291***
Having difficulty in communication	0.1534***	0.1415***	4.6541***	4.4908***
Having difficulty in psycho-social domain	0.0777***	0.0813***	2.5613***	2.6652***
Kinh (Kinh=1, ethnic minorities=0)		-0.0210*		0.7033*
Single				
Married		-0.0285**		0.5173***
Widowed		-0.0201*		0.5699
Divorced or separate		-0.0105		0.7529
Less than primary education				
Primary education		-0.0046		0.9457
Lower-secondary education		-0.0130**		0.7589*
Upper-secondary education		-0.0064		0.9100
Post secondary education		0.0007		0.9886
Living with a member aged 15-59				

Explanatory variables	Marginal effect from Probit		Odds ratio from Logit	
	Small model	Large model	Small model	Large model
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
Living alone		0.0106		1.2014
Living with only children and/or elderly		0.0047		1.1170
Household size		0.0030**		1.0696**
Poorest wealth quintile				
Near-poorest wealth quintile		0.0101		1.2375*
Middle wealth quintile		0.0153*		1.3701**
Near-richest wealth quintile		0.0134		1.3072*
Richest wealth quintile		0.0076		1.1746
Urban areas (urban=1, rural=0)		0.0011		1.0733
Red River Delta				
Northern Mountain		-0.0130		0.7276
Central Coast		0.0003		0.9786
Central Highland		-0.0142*		0.6717*
Southeast		0.0084		1.1323
Mekong River Delta		0.0112		1.3027
Constant			0.0022**	0.0050**
Observations			(0.0056)	(0.0134)
Pseudo R-squared	15.372	15.372	15.372	15.372

Source: Estimation from the 2016 VNDS. Note: Robust standard errors are corrected for sampling weight and intra-cluster correlation. To avoid lengthy results, this table does not report standard errors. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.